

Design Optimization and Simulation of a 2.4 GHz Circularly Polarized Helical Antenna

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Abstract – The design and performance evaluation of a 2.4 GHz helical antenna for efficient wireless communication in environments with significant signal reflections is presented in this study. Helical antennas, known for their ability to provide circular polarization and high directivity, are an ideal solution for minimizing interference in such challenging conditions. The antenna is designed with key parameters, including helix diameter, turn spacing, and pitch angle, and is optimized for 2.4 GHz frequency operation. A detailed method using theoretical equations guides the design process, ensuring precision in performance. The evaluated antenna exhibits a low return loss of -30.89 dB, a voltage standing wave ratio of 1.05, and high directivity and gain values of 8.08 dBi and 8.23 dBi, respectively. These results demonstrate that the proposed helical antenna meets the performance requirements for modern wireless communication applications, offering a reliable solution for systems such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and IoT networks.

Keywords – Helical Antenna, 2.4 GHz Frequency, Axial Mode, Circular Polarization

I. INTRODUCTION

Antennas are essential components in modern communication systems, acting as transducers that convert electrical signals into electromagnetic waves for transmission or vice versa. They serve as the interface between electrical circuits and the electromagnetic environment, enabling technologies such as radio, television, radar, satellite, and wireless networks to facilitate reliable data transmission. The antenna area, which encompasses the electromagnetic fields around it, is crucial for understanding the interaction between the antenna and its environment. Analyzing this region helps study the behavior of electromagnetic waves and their transition from guided waves in transmission lines to free-space radiation, which is vital for efficient signal propagation and optimizing antenna performance [1,2].

Helical antennas, introduced by John D. Kraus, are widely used for applications requiring circular polarization and high directivity. These antennas, composed of a wire wound in a helical shape around a cylindrical surface, are simple to construct and offer broad bandwidth, making them ideal for satellite communications, wireless networks, and other applications. Key design parameters such as the number of turns, pitch angle, circumference, and axial ratio influence their performance, including gain, radiation pattern, and impedance matching [3]. Helical antennas are particularly effective at the 2.4 GHz frequency, which lies within the industrial, scientific, and medical (ISM) band, and are widely used for technologies like WI-FI, Bluetooth, and ZigBee. This frequency balances signal propagation and antenna size, making it ideal for compact designs and efficient data transmission. Helical antennas are classified into two types: normal-mode and axial-mode. Normal-mode helical antennas are typically used for omnidirectional radiation patterns.

In contrast, axial-mode helical antennas, with a helix circumference comparable to the wavelength, are suited for directional radiation and high directivity. The axial mode enhances performance in end-fire or traveling wave applications, making these antennas suitable for systems requiring high directivity, such as first-person view (FPV) systems for drones [4]. Studies, such as those by Setiawan et al., have demonstrated helix antennas in FPV systems operating at 5.8 GHz, optimizing video transmission for aerial communication [5]. In wireless LAN communications at 2.4 GHz, helix antennas offer compact size and superior performance, increasingly replacing traditional antennas in consumer electronics and communication networks [6].

Recent advancements in helix antenna design have further enhanced their applications across various domains. For example, research on deploying helix antenna systems for CubeSat applications has demonstrated their effectiveness in satellite communication, achieving a gain of 11.44 dB at 1575.42 MHz [7]. Furthermore, integrating low-temperature cofired ceramic (LTCC) quad-phase power splitting networks with ceramic-based quadrifilar helical antennas has shown promising results for satellite communication, offering low power consumption and high reliability [8]. Helical antennas have also been explored for underwater communication, with designs such as the Bow-Tie microstrip antenna developed by Karagianni et al. to address high path loss in underwater environments, demonstrating the potential of RF technology for sensor networks [9]. Additionally, Talkar and Fernandes simulated a monopole antenna for sea surface communication at 2.4 GHz, designed to withstand harsh underwater conditions such as temperature and pressure variations [10]. Further innovations include incorporating circular parasitic rings inside helical antennas, as explored by Kim et al., which improved antenna performance by 2.5 dB without increasing its size, offering a compact solution for high-performance applications [11]. In underwater wireless communication, Lloret et al. compared the performance of RF, acoustic, and optical communication systems, concluding that RF communication, particularly at 2.4 GHz, offers higher data transfer rates over shorter distances, making it suitable for precise monitoring applications and high-depth communication systems [12].

This research focuses on designing and evaluating a 2.4 GHz helical antenna specifically tailored for effective signal transmission in environments with significant signal reflections. By operating in axial mode, the antenna provides circular polarization, high directivity, and reduced interference from multipath signals. The aim is to enhance the antenna's directivity and half-power beamwidth (HPBW), improving performance in practical applications while achieving low return loss and optimized functionality.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A helical antenna is selected due to its ability to provide circular polarization, a feature particularly useful in environments with numerous obstacles that cause significant signal reflection. It is preferred for its directional radiation pattern, unlike the normal-mode helical antenna, which radiates omnidirectional.

Designing a helical antenna involves interconnected calculations that enhance its efficiency and performance. Fig. 1 illustrates the antenna's geometry, emphasizing key parameters. The design begins with determining the operating frequency of 2.4 GHz and performance requirements, such as gain and bandwidth. The wavelength, calculated using Equation (1), serves as the foundation for establishing parameters such as helix diameter (D), turn spacing (S), total height (L), and circumference (C) as given in Equation (3). The axial length of one turn (L_0) and the helix angle (α) are defined using Equation (5). The base structure, often integrated with a ground plane, ensures robust signal transmission or reception. In addition to these geometric parameters, the helical antenna's directivity and half-power beamwidth (HPBW) are critical for its application in communication systems. The phase progression and electric field patterns must be computed to optimize performance for normal end-fire and Hansen-Woodyard modes. The antenna operates in axial mode to achieve high directivity and circular polarization, which is critical for reliable performance in environments with signal reflections. Input impedance is optimized to match transmitter or receiver systems effectively, ensuring efficient power transfer.

This study follows standard design procedures. Each process step, from wavelength determination to radiation pattern evaluation, is supported by detailed equations to validate theoretical models and enhance practical implementation, ensuring accuracy and reliability. The wavelength is calculated using [1].

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f} \tag{1}$$

For a chosen frequency of 2.4 GHz, where $c=3 \times 10^8$, the calculated wavelength is 0.125m. To effectively excite the axial mode, the helical antenna's diameter (D) and turn spacing (S) must be large enough fractions of the wavelength (λ), as these parameters are crucial for achieving the desired radiation properties.

$$s = \frac{\lambda}{4} \tag{2}$$

Circular polarization, a key characteristic of axial mode operation, is mainly achieved in the major lobe when the helix circumference (C) falls within the range. 0.75λ to 1.33λ with the optimal value typically around $\frac{C}{\lambda} = 1$ as shown in Equation (3).

$$\frac{3}{4} \leq \frac{C}{\lambda} \leq \frac{4}{3} \tag{3}$$

Where diameter is related to the circumference as given by

$$D = \frac{C}{\pi} \tag{4}$$

Furthermore, the spacing between the turns (S) should be approximately $\lambda/4$, as given in Equation (2), to ensure the antenna operates efficiently. The pitch angle (α), which defines the helical structure and influences the polarization and radiation pattern, is usually set between $12^\circ < \alpha < 14^\circ$, offering a balanced compromise between performance and mechanical design.

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{S}{C} \right) \tag{5}$$

Fig. 1 Geometric configuration and design parameters of a helical antenna [1]

In most cases, the antenna is integrated with a ground plane, which enhances its performance by reflecting and directing the radiated waves, thus increasing gain and optimizing signal transmission or reception.

$$D_o = 15 \cdot \left(\frac{C^2 \cdot n \cdot S}{\lambda^3} \right) \quad (6)$$

The directivity of a helical antenna depends on its mode of operation. For axial mode operation, where the helix radiates along its axis, the directivity can be expressed as Equation (6). Where D_o is the directivity (dimensionless or in dBi when converted), n is the number of turns in the helix, C is the circumference of the helix where S is the spacing between the turns (S), and λ is the wavelength of operation. In Equation (7), the total physical length of the helical antenna depends on the number of turns (n) and the spacing between turns (S). This relationship determines the overall size and structure of the antenna.

$$L_{total} = n \times S \quad (7)$$

Equation (8) shows that the half-power beamwidth (HPBW) defines the angular width of the main lobe at the power points. As the number of turns (n) and the spacing (S) increase, the beam narrows, improving the antenna's directivity and focusing the radiation in a specific direction.

$$HPBW = \frac{52^\circ \times \lambda \times \sqrt{\lambda}}{C \times \sqrt{nS}} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, Equation (9) describes the first null beamwidth (FNBW), the angular width between the first nulls in the radiation pattern. A larger number of turns results in a narrower beamwidth, increasing the antenna's directional gain.

$$FNBW = \frac{115^\circ \times \lambda^{\frac{3}{2}}}{C \times \sqrt{nS}} \quad (9)$$

Equation (10) introduces the axial ratio (AR), which measures the purity of circular polarization. As the number of turns increases, the axial ratio approaches 1, indicating improved circular polarization, which is desirable for specific communication applications.

$$AR = \frac{2n+1}{2n} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 2 shows the proposed 2.4 GHz helical antenna, featuring a helical conductor wound with a precise pitch angle and mounted on a circular ground plane.

Fig. 2 Geometry of the 2.4 GHz helical antenna

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the proposed 2.4 GHz helical antenna has been evaluated using several important parameters essential for assessing its practical applications. These include a Teflon diameter measuring 0.35 mm. The SMA pin diameter is 1 mm, and the disk diameter is 10 mm. These dimensions are critical as they directly influence the antenna's radiation properties and impedance matching. One of the most significant results from evaluating the antenna's performance is its return loss, measured at -30.89 dB at the operating frequency of 2.4 GHz, as shown in Fig. 3. This return loss level indicates minimal power is reflected to the source, confirming that the antenna is well-matched to the transmission line. A high return loss signifies efficient energy transmission, which is important for optimizing the antenna's performance in real-world applications. Generally, a return loss greater than -10 dB is considered acceptable, and the proposed antenna comfortably exceeds this threshold, showing its suitability for use in wireless communication systems.

Fig. 3 Return loss

The antenna's voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) is measured at 1.05, as shown in Fig. 4, which is extremely low. This indicates that the antenna performs optimally, with minimal standing waves along the transmission line. A VSWR of 1.05 signifies a low impedance mismatch, which is important for ensuring that the antenna radiates the maximum amount of power instead of reflecting it. In wireless communication, low VSWR is essential for maintaining signal quality and preventing losses. Therefore, this antenna is an ideal choice for applications that require consistent performance.

Fig. 4 VSWR

The proposed antenna's return loss (S_{11}) characteristics are shown in Fig. 5, illustrating its performance over the 2–3 GHz frequency range. The S_{11} parameter indicates the frequency range where the antenna exhibits low reflection loss, which is crucial for efficient power transfer. As observed, the return loss crosses the -10 dB threshold at two distinct points, resulting in a 43 MHz bandwidth centered around 2.4 GHz. This demonstrates that the antenna achieves sufficient bandwidth for reliable operation, with minimal reflection losses across the designated frequency range.

Fig. 5 S_{11} Parameter showing bandwidth and reflection loss

The antenna has a directivity of 8.08 dBi and a gain of 8.23 dBi at the 2.4 GHz resonant frequency, as shown in Fig. 6. Directivity measures how focused an antenna's radiation pattern is in a specific direction. In contrast, gain evaluates the antenna's effectiveness in converting input power into radio waves. The relatively high values of both directivity and gain indicate that the antenna can transmit energy effectively to a specific location. This capability is particularly useful for point-to-point communication and remote sensing applications. The gain value suggests that the antenna can significantly enhance signal strength, which is advantageous for increasing communication range and reliability.

Fig. 6. Directivity and gain

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed 2.4 GHz helical antenna has excellent performance characteristics, such as a high return loss, low VSWR, and significant directivity and gain. These characteristics make it a perfect option for wireless communication applications like WI-FI, Bluetooth, and other RF systems. The design parameters and its performance indicate the antenna's potential to meet the requirements of current communication

technologies, which leads to efficient and reliable transmission of signals. Future research could focus on enhancing the antenna design to improve its performance in various frequency bands and applications and analyzing the impact of environmental conditions on operating efficiency.

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